

“Knowledge doesn’t benefit anyone if it’s inaccessible.”

Martin Paul Eve, Professor
of Literature, Technology
and Publishing at Birkbeck,
University of London

Research has impact when people can access it, engage with it and build on it.

Eve firmly believes that open access book publishing enables that greater impact, facilitating the dissemination of knowledge by removing geographical and financial barriers. He says this creates a more equitable world, one where scholars and people everywhere can easily find and use knowledge. Eve has mobility issues so open access publishing enables him to access knowledge easily, while at the same time amplifying his voice through enabling him to reach a wider audience.

He says: “It’s had a very positive impact on my career. And I have much greater satisfaction and purpose in what I do, knowing there’s a much broader audience for my work. People who don’t engage with open access are missing out on a huge opportunity to do good in the world.”

Eve says open access book publishing drives impact

It breaks down access
barriers

Access drives engagement
and that creates impact

It disseminates research
to a bigger, wider audience

Knowledge is used and
built on more widely

Improved access
encourages diversity
of thinking and debate